

Distribution of Heavy Metals in Surface Water and Sediments of Mini-Ngulo Stream in Isiokpo Ikwerre Local Government Area Rivers State, Nigeria

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Abstract

The study of heavy metal distribution in surface water and sediment for the Mini-Ngulo Stream in Isiokpo, Rivers State was carried out due to the economic significance. The water samples were collected adhering to water safety standards including sieving, drying, acid digestion and measurements. The heavy metal levels were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy-Agilent sps 4 models MY17090001 with appropriate lamps and standards (AS/NZS5667, 1999). The results of heavy metal levels in the stations ranged from 0.054 ± 0.08 to 1.079 ± 1.26 mg/l for zinc, BDL to 0.003 ± 0.004 mg/l for cadmium, BDL for nickel, 0.031 ± 0.051 to 0.168 ± 0.202 mg/l for lead, 0.431 ± 0.438 to 0.589 ± 0.766 mg/l for manganese and 0.042 ± 0.158 to 0.249 ± 0.407 mg/l for chromium. The distribution pattern indicates that the concentration of manganese and chromium were high across the different stations. Relatively higher concentrations of heavy metals in the sediment as against the surface water were indicative of overtime pollution of the river and confirmation of the sediment as a sink for heavy metals especially for Cd, Ni, Mn and Cr. There is need to monitor the pollution load of this stream due to its economic importance to the residents of Isiokpo and its environs.

Keywords: *Mini-Ngulo, Isiokpo, heavy metals, chromium, surface water, sediment.*

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Introduction

The presence of heavy metals in water and sediment has become an issue of concern advocates of healthy aquatic environment. Heavy metals in aquatic environment originate from geochemistry of the drainage basin, mining activities, discharge of industrial wastes, agricultural runoff among other factors influence deposition and accumulation of heavy metals in sediments as they readily associates with particulates in water and ultimately settle in bottom sediments in regions of calm water (Iwegbue *et al.*, 2012). other anthropogenic activities (Venktesha *et al.*, 2016).

Heavy metals are among the critical pollutants investigated in environmental because of their persistence, non-biodegradability and toxicity. Sediments play a major role in influencing pollution of rivers and can be used to record the history of river pollution (Yu *et al.*, 2001; Wepener & Vermulen, 2005). Thus sediments provide essential information for evaluating ambient environmental quality conditions in aquatic ecosystem (Nwajei *et al.*, 2014). The toxicity and persistence of heavy metals in aquatic environment and their accumulation in aquatic food chain threatens the survival of man as high uptake of heavy metals is associated with serious health conditions. A strong association exists between contaminated drinking water with trace elements and the incidence of chronic diseases such as renal failure, liver cirrhosis, hair loss and chronic anemia (Johri *et al.*, 2010). For instance high cadmium and lead concentrations in water has been implicated for permanent damage to the central nervous system, brain and kidney (Johri *et al.*, 2010).

Assessments of heavy metal levels in surface water and sediments in several locations around the world have revealed staggering concentration of lead, manganese, chromium, nickel, cadmium, iron and zinc in surface water and bottom sediments of water bodies. Edokpai *et al.*(2016) investigated trace metal contamination of surface water as well as sediment and reported that average concentration of aluminium, chromium, iron, manganese and lead in surface water exceeded

recommended limits for drinking water. They concluded that the river was polluted by the discharge of partially treated waste water effluent from Thohoyandou waste water treatment plant, agricultural runoff, land fill site and other non-point sources. Saha and Hossain (2011) determined the heavy metal concentration and sediment quality in Buriganga River, Bangladesh and observed high mean concentration of lead, cadmium, chromium, copper and zinc; and concluded that the sediments was contaminated. In a similar study, Tang *et al.* (2014). Investigated metal concentration in sediments of representative limnetic ecosystem in eastern China and reported high heavy metal levels in sediments. Ideriah *et al.* (2012) assessed the distribution of heavy metals in water and sediments and observed that the concentration of metals and their pollution index values in sediments were high.

The sublime danger posed by elevated heavy metal uptake and the dearth of research data on heavy metal distribution on surface water and sediment of Mini-Ngulo stream prompted the investigation. The aim of the study is to assess the distribution of heavy metal in surface water and sediment of Mini-Ngulo stream with the view to provide baseline data of the surface water and sediments for future monitoring programme.

Materials and Methods

Study Area

Mini-Ngulo is a black freshwater stream that takes its rise at Isokpo and empties into Aluu-Choba River system-a tributary of the new Calabar River. It is non-tidal along the stretch covering four sampling stations, but the fifth station experiences tidal inflow. The sampling stations lies within coordinates N05° 01'09.3" to N04°05'08.3" and E006°52' 24.2" to E006°52'65.9" on the Global Position System. It is situated in the fringes of an upcoming city with a major industrial concern; however the stream drains the community receiving storm water.

Mini-Ngulo is located in the low land rainforest region of the Niger Delta which is characterized by a tropical climate with long wet season mainly from March/ April to November. The wet

season last nearly throughout the year with peak in July/August and the dry months are mainly between December and February (Hughes & Hughes 1992). Mini- Ngulo is rich in biodiversity having diverse species of flora and fauna. The dominant rainforest vegetation consists largely of soft stemmed plant such as ferns, vines, mosses, raphia, bamboo and other non-timber microphytes. These microphytes secrete two or more organics and hence play major roles in water quality determination (Reddy & Reddy 2011). Fauna species consist of water snail (*Pila Ovata*) fresh water crayfish (*Paranephrops Planifrons*), topminnow fish among which is (*Labidestha Siccuslus*), *Clarias garieinus*, *Heterobranchus longifilis*, *oreochronus niloticus*, *Chrysichthys nigrodigitatus* and *Microbrachin sp.* Uzukwu *et al.* (2014); and many such fishes that are found in freshwater at Aluu stretch of the stream.

The geology of Mini-Ngulo stream is typical of the Niger Delta Basin that forms part of the geological sequence of the tertiary and quaternary formation of the Niger Delta consisting largely of Agbada geologic formation and Akata formation. The soil type is of the Warri-Deltaic sand (Agbozu & Ekweozor, 2001).

Sample Collection and Preservation

Thirty (30) surface water and sediment samples each were collected along the fresh water course of Mini-Ngulo into various containers. Samples for measurement of heavy metal in surface were collected in plastic containers and few drops of concentrated nitric acid were added. Sediment samples were collected with plastic shovel sampler at each sampling point at about 2 to 4cm on the streambed and transfer into a labeled plastic bag. The collected samples were stored in an ice chest for onward transportation to the laboratory. In the laboratory, the sediment samples were air-dried, sieved with 2mm mesh size and preserved in brown paper.

Sample Analysis

Digestion of Water Sample and Heavy Metal Level Determination

100ml of surface water sample was measured and transferred into a beaker followed by the

addition of 5ml concentrated nitric acid. The beaker and its content were placed on a hot plate and evaporated to about 20ml. The beaker was cooled and another 5ml concentrated nitric acid was added and returned to the hot plate for further heating. During heating, small portion of concentrated nitric acid was added until the solution was light coloured and clear. After cooling, the beaker and watch glass were washed with distilled water into a filter paper-funnel arrangement and filtered to remove some insoluble materials that could clog the atomizer. The filtrate was poured into a 100ml flask and the volume adjusted to 100ml with distilled water. The heavy metal levels were analyzed using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy-Agilent sps 4 models MY17090001 with appropriate lamps and standards (AS/NZS5667, 1999).

Digestion of Sediment and Heavy Metal Determination

Sediment samples was air-dried in the laboratory, fragments found in the sediments were removed and uniformly mixed by pulverizing. Sediments were then sieved through a 2mm sieve to remove coarse particles. 0.5 g of the sieved sediment sample was weighed and put into acid washed glass beaker. 20ml of aqua-regia was added to the sample for digestion and another 10ml of 30% hydrogen peroxide was added to prevent overflow of broth from the beaker which may lead to the loss of substance from the beaker. The beaker was then covered with a watch glass and heated over a hot plate at 90°C for two hours. After cooling the content of the beaker was transferred into a filter paper funnel arrangement and the supernatant liquid filtered out into a 100ml volumetric flask from the insoluble solid. The volume was diluted to 100ml with distilled water. The heavy metal levels were determined using Atomic Absorption Spectroscopy (AAS) with appropriate lamps and standards.

Results and Discussion

Spatial distribution of heavy metal concentration in surface water and sediment are presented in Tables 1 and 2. Data obtained are compared with national and international standards such as Nigerian standards for drinking water (NSDW), Department of petroleum Resources/ Federal

Ministry of Environment (DPR/FMEn) and World Health Organization (WHO) to ascertain conformity of measured parameter with permissible standards.

Heavy Metal Levels in Surface Water

The results of heavy metal levels in the stations ranged from 0.054 ± 0.08 to 1.079 ± 1.26 mg/l for zinc, BDL to 0.003 ± 0.004 mg/l for cadmium, BDL for nickel, 0.031 ± 0.051 to 0.168 ± 0.202 mg/l for lead, 0.431 ± 0.438 to 0.589 ± 0.766 mg/l for manganese and 0.042 ± 0.158 to 0.249 ± 0.407 mg/l for chromium. The distribution pattern indicates that the concentration of manganese and chromium was

high across the different stations. This may be attributed to a combination of natural sources, domestic waste disposal and storm water intrusion (Itekere *et al.*, 2024; Iyama *et al.*, 2017; Iyama *et al.*, 2018).

The overall heavy metal levels in the study area compared favourably with results obtained from another study in the Niger Delta region (Nwankwoala & Angaya, 2017). However, the result of the finding for manganese and chromium exceeded WHO and NSDW permissible limits for drinking water of 0.1 mg/l and 0.02 mg/l respectively as earlier reported earlier (Iyama *et al.*, 2020).

Table 1. Heavy Metal Characteristics of Mini-Ngulo in Surface Water

Metals mg/kg	ST-01	ST-02	ST-03	ST-04	ST-05	WHO	NSDW
Zn	0.054 ± 0.079	0.544 ± 0.619	1.079 ± 1.263	0.159 ± 0.136	0.153 ± 0.156	5	-
Cd	BDL	BDL	0.003 ± 0.004	0.003 ± 0.003	0.002 ± 0.002	0.03	-
Ni	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	BDL	0.01	0.05
Pb	0.032 ± 0.062	0.031 ± 0.051	0.168 ± 0.202	0.031 ± 0.040	0.560 ± 0.674	0.1	0.1
Mn	0.486 ± 0.619	0.499 ± 0.692	0.589 ± 0.766	0.431 ± 0.483	0.526 ± 0.674	0.1	0.005
Cr	0.044 ± 0.059	0.042 ± 0.158	0.092 ± 0.118	0.064 ± 0.085	0.025 ± 0.407	0.05	0.02

Figure 1. Spatial Distribution of Heavy Metals in Surface Water of Mini-Ngulo Stream

Heavy Metal Levels in Sediment

The heavy metal concentration in sediments across the stations ranged from 0.03 ± 0.01 to 0.0353 ± 0.12 mg/kg for zinc, 0.002 ± 0.001 to 0.029 ± 0.023 mg/kg for cadmium, BDL to 0.015 ± 0.014 mg/kg for nickel, 0.033 ± 0.028 to

0.347 ± 0.405 mg/kg for lead, 0.405 ± 0.342 to 1.109 ± 0.752 mg/kg for manganese and 0.094 ± 0.018 to 0.407 ± 0.303 mg/kg for chromium. The overall trace metal levels in sediment compares favourably with the findings of other researcher (Upadhi *et al.*, 2013; Akporido & Ipeiyeda 2014; Itekere *et al.*, 2024). However

values observed from sediments of Bonny River and Bohai-China far exceeds those reported in this study (Zhou *et al.*, 2014; Buba *et al.*, 2017). A Comparison of these values with DPR/FME standards indicated that they were below the recommended limits of heavy metal levels in sediments. The low high metal concentration in sediments may be ascribed to the absence of industrial and large scale agricultural activities in

the area. Relatively higher concentrations of heavy metals in the sediment as against the surface water were indicative of overtime pollution of the river and confirmation of the sediment as a sink for heavy metals especially for Cd, Ni, Mn and Cr (Olu *et al.*, 2019; Itekere *et al.*, 2024). The spatial variation in heavy metal concentration for the Mini-Ngulo stream is showed in Figure 2.

Table 2. Heavy Metal Characteristics of Mini-Ngulo in Sediments

H.Metals mg/kg	ST-01	ST-02	ST-03	ST-04	ST-05	DPR
Zn	0.276± 0.165	0.198±0.244	0.353±0.115	0.298±0.010	0.272±0.011	140
Cd	0.008± 0.012	0.002± 0.01	0.009±0.011	0.029±0.023	0.007±0.003	0.8
Ni	0.005± 0.006	0.015± 0.014	0.001± 0.002	BDL	BDL	35
Pb	0.347±0.405	0.050±0.022	0.186±0.144	0.033±0.028	0.035±0.040	85
Mn	0.571±0.419	0.405±0.342	0.577±0.406	0.938±0.691	1.109±0.752	473
Cr	0.094±0.018	0.267±0.185	0.114±0.069	0.145±0.142	0.407±0.303	100

Figure 2. Spatial Distribution of Heavy Metals in Sediments of Mini-Ngulo Seam

Figure 3. Spatial Distribution of Heavy Metal Concentrations for Surface Water and Sediments in Mini-Ngulo Stream

Conclusion

The concentration of heavy metals in surface water and sediments of Mini-Ngulo stream were generally low and within recommended threshold. However, the levels of manganese and chromium in surface water exceeded NSDW and WHO permissible limits for drinking water while metal levels in sediments were below DPR standards. Therefore, the economic importance of this black freshwater to the people of Isiokpo and its environs needs to be enhanced and protected by regular monitoring and avoidance of community anthropogenic inputs deleterious to public health.

Reference

- Agbozu, I. E., & Ekweozor, I. K. W. (2001). Heavy metals in non-tidal fresh water swamp in the Niger Delta area of Nigeria. *African Journal of Science*, 21, 175–182.
- Akporido, S. O., & Ipeaiyeda, A. R. (2014). An assessment of the oil and toxic heavy metal profiles of sediments of the Benin River adjacent to a lubricating oil producing factory, Delta State, Nigeria. *International Research Journal of Public and Environmental Health*, 1(12), 40–53.
- Australia Standard/New Zealand Standard (AS/NZS 5667.12). (1999). *Water quality—Sampling—Guidance on the sampling of bottom sediments, Part 12*.
- Bubu, A., Onunugbo, C. P., & Avwiri, G. O. (2017). Determination of heavy metal concentration in sediment of Bonny River, Nigeria. *Archives of Current Research International*, 11(14), 1–11.
- Edokpayi, J. N., Odiyo, J. O., Popoola, O. E., & Msagati, T. A. M. (2016). Assessment of trace metal concentration of surface water and sediment: A case study of Mvudi River, South Africa. *Sustainability*, 8(2), 135. <https://doi.org/10.3390/su8020135>
- Hughes, R. H., & Hughes, J. S. (1992). *A directory of African wetlands*. International Union for Conservation of Nature.
- Ideriah, T. J. K., David-Omiema, S., & Ogbonna, D. N. (2012). Distribution of heavy metals in water and sediment along Abonnema shoreline, Nigeria. *Resources and Environment*, 2(1), 33–40.
- Itekere, S., Iyama, W. A., Obunwo, C. C., Gobo, A. E., & Nwagbara, V. U. (2024). Pollution load index of the Mini-Chida Stream, Port Harcourt, Nigeria. *Applied Sciences Research Periodicals*, 2(10), 91–104.
- Iwegbue, C. M. A., Arimoro, F. O., Nwajei, G. E., & Eguavoen, O. I. (2012). Concentration and distribution of trace metals in water and streambed sediments of Orogodo River, Southern Nigeria: Soil and sediment contamination. *Soil and Sediment Contamination: An International Journal*, 21(3), 382–406. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15320383.2012.672487>
- Iyama, W. A., Eugene-Nwala, O., & Igoni, I. (2017). Assessment of the various physicochemical parameters and heavy metals pollution potentials of Ekerikana water body, Rivers State, Nigeria. *International Journal of Chemistry, Pharmacy and Technology*, 2(43), 162–168.
- Iyama, W. A., Edori, O. S., & Ede, P. N. (2018). Heavy metals and nutrient status of surface water quality around Sagbama Creek, Bayelsa State, Nigeria. *Journal of Applied Chemical Science International*, 9(3–4), 161–167.
- Iyama, W. A., Edori, O. S., & Nwagbara, V. U. (2020). Assessment of the pollution load of the Woji Creek water body, Port Harcourt, Rivers State, South-South, Nigeria. *International Journal of Advanced Research in Chemical Science (IJARCS)*, 7(1), 1–8. <http://dx.doi.org/10.20431/2349-0403.0701001>
- Johri, N., Jacquillet, G., & Unwin, R. (2010). Heavy metal poisoning: The effects of cadmium

on the kidney. *Biometals*, 23(5), 783–792. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10534-010-9328-y>

Nwajei, G. E., Dibofori-Orji, A. N., Iwegbue, C. M. A., & Ojuh, B. O. (2014). Distribution of trace elements in surface water and sediments from Crayford Creek in Warri, Delta State of Nigeria. *Academic Research International*, 5(4), 123–134.

Nwankwoala, H. O., & Angaya, Y. B. (2017). An evaluation of heavy metal concentration in the Choba section of the New Calabar River, Eastern Niger Delta. *Biodiversity International Journal*, 1(6), 163–176.

Olu, U., Ugbomeh, A. P., Bob-Manuel, K. N. O., & Ekweozor, I. K. E. (2019). Levels of selected heavy metals in water and sediment of the Soku Oil Field area of the Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Journal of Aquatic Pollution and Toxicology*, 3(1), 25. <https://doi.org/10.21767/2581-804X.100025>

Reddy, P. G., & Reddy, G. V. S. (2011). Physicochemical analysis of surface and ground water of selected area of Ucil, India. *African Journal of Science Research*, 3(1), 163–176.

Saha, P. K., & Hossain, M. D. (2011). Assessment of heavy metal contamination and sediment quality in the Buriganga River, Bangladesh. In *2nd International Conference on Environment and Technology International Proceeding of Chemical Biological and Environment*.

Tang, W., Shan, B., Zhang, H., Zhang, W., Zhao, Y., Ding, Y., Rong, N., & Zhu, X. (2014). Heavy metal contamination in the surface sediments of

representative limnetic ecosystems in eastern China. *Scientific Reports*, 4, 7152. <https://doi.org/10.1038/srep07152>

Upadhi, F., Wokoma, O. A. F., & Edoghotu, J. A. (2013). Levels of bioaccumulation of some heavy metals in fish (*Tilapia zilli*) and their concentrations in water and sediment of Owubu Creek, Niger Delta, Nigeria. *Resources and Environment*, 3(3), 59–64.

Venktesha, R. K., Somashekar, R. K., & Prakash, K. L. (2012). Heavy metal status of sediment in River Cauvery, Karnataka. *Environmental Monitoring and Assessment*, 184(1), 361–373. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10661-011-1965-1>

Wepener, V., & Vermeulen, L. A. (2005). Concentration and biodiversity of selected metals in sediments of Richards Bay Harbour, South Africa. *Water SA*, 31(4), 589–596. <https://doi.org/10.4314/wsa.v31i4.5144>

Yu, K. C., Tsai, L. J., Chen, S. H., & Ho, S. T. (2001). Correlation analysis on binding behavior of heavy metals with sediment matrices. *Water Research*, 35(10), 2417–2428. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354\(00\)00506-8](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0043-1354(00)00506-8)

Zhou, R., Qin, X., Peng, S., & Deng, S. (2014). Total petroleum hydrocarbons and heavy metals in the surface sediments of Bohai Bay, China: Long-term variations in pollution status and adverse biological risk. *Marine Pollution Bulletin*, 83(1), 290–297. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.marpolbul.2014.03.020>